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Encouragement Through Creative Reading and Writing Activities

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Abstract: This study attempts to explore the enhancement of encouragement skills through creative reading and writing activities. The sample of the study consisted of 1020 students in the last two grades of primary school of which 679 students participated in 13 creative reading and writing workshops and 341 students followed the school's curriculum. The results, which were obtained from the analysis of teachers' responses, showed the positive correlation between reinforcement of encouragement and creative reading/writing. The significance of the results is due to the fact that encouragement is a key characteristic of human development and also of a good relationship with others.

Keywords: encouragement, creative reading, creative writing

Introduction

Alfred Adler in 1956 was the first psychologist to develop the theory of encouragement, which he considered a key feature of human development. For Sweeney (2009), encouragement means to inspire or help others in their efforts to find solutions or to cope with any difficult situation. For Main and Boughner (2011), encouragement is necessary when people lose their social interest since they have an inherent desire to belong and respond to society.

As far as children are concerned, they need encouragement *“like a plant that needs sun and water”* (Dreikurs & Cassel, 1972: 74), as the lack of it can lead to a bad behaviour (Dreikurs & Soltz, 1964), while at the same time it is a requirement in every endeavour, but also a belief that they will not succeed (Dinkmeyer, McKay & Carlson, 1979). It should be emphasized that in school, encouragement should come not only from the teacher, but also from peers, which can lead to positive academic and social outcomes (Patrick et al, 2007) and enhance a sense of belonging (Hamm & Faircloth, 2005). At this point, we should clarify that peer encouragement can be divided into active and passive. The first involves verbal encouragement of peers to engage in a particular behaviour (Arnett, 2007), while the other involves imitation and observation of their behaviour (Harakeh & De Boer, 2018).

Research Aim and Research Questions

The aim of this research is to investigate the extent to which creative reading and writing activities, using a variety of textual genres as a stimulus, can contribute to the enhancement of the skill of encouragement for students in the last two grades of primary school. Specifically, the research questions are as follows:

Through creative reading and writing activities will students' ability to:

1. support and praise others for their effort?
2. use humour to create a positive climate in the groups they work in?

Research Results

Several studies have shown that creative reading and writing activities can help to strengthen students within the school context. Arshavskaya's (2015) research highlighted creative writing as a mean of encouraging students with low learning motivation to engage more actively and enjoyably in a variety of creative writing activities, while Maher's (2018) research concluded that reading and writing literature encourages children through interaction with their peers to approach texts, process and discuss them, seeking meaning and ideas. It would be remiss not to highlight the encouraging role of creative writing in addressing emotional tensions, expressing feelings and enhancing empathy (Hojat, 2007; Pennebaker, 1997; Wright, 2005).

The above findings are in line with the research of Jankowska and Atlay (2008) which studies the effect of teaching on students' engagement in the learning process in a specially designed creative learning space. The study involved 43 staff members from the University of Bedfordshire in the UK and 39 students and showed that a specially designed creative space encourages students' active participation in the learning process by promoting discussion, problem solving and multiple thinking skills.

In the present survey 1020 students of the last two grades of primary school took part. Of these, 679 took part in 13 creative reading and writing workshops (intervention group), while 341 followed the school programme (control group). All students participated in the study by completing two evaluation questionnaires (initial and final) by the teachers, who answered the above research

questions. Teachers' ratings of students are presented in the form of means and standard deviations for each of the assessments (pre- and post-intervention) and for each group of students [Table 1].

Table 1

Descriptive statistics for teachers' ratings of students before and after the intervention by student group

Encouragement	Evaluation	Group			
		Control		Intervention	
		Average	Standard deviation	Average	Standard deviation
	Initial	3.41	1.00	3.45	0.92
	Final	3.57	1.01	3.79	0.83

It is observed that teachers have assessed the skill of encouragement after the intervention with a higher degree, on average, compared to the degree before the intervention for both groups of students. Furthermore, it appears that teachers have assessed the skill of encouragement post-intervention to a greater extent for the students in the intervention group compared to the same skill for the students in the control group.

It should be clarified that teachers' ratings of students' post-intervention were compared between the two groups of students (Control and Intervention) for the skill of encouragement by applying ANCOVA (Analysis of Covariance). These comparisons are made after controlling for (removing) the effect of the pre-intervention assessment on the post-intervention assessment (as would be the case if all students had the same pre-intervention assessment).

Below are the results of the ANCOVA and adjusted averages for the post-intervention assessment scores obtained after controlling (removing) for the effect of the pre-intervention assessment on the post-intervention assessment [Table 2].

Table 2

Results of the comparisons between the two groups of students (Control and Intervention) in relation to teachers' post-intervention ratings of the skill of encouragement and with the corresponding pre-intervention ratings as covariates (ANCOVA)

	Group				F (1, 1017)	p
	Control		Intervention			
Encouragement	Average	Standard error	Average	Standard error		
	3,58	0,04	3,78	0,03	21,03	< 0,001

According to the adjusted averages, teachers have assessed the skill of encouragement of students in the Intervention group as higher than the corresponding skill of students in the Control group with a statistically significant difference ($p < 0.001$).

Conclusions

The findings of the present study document the use of creative reading and writing as an effective tool to enhance the skill of encouragement. Statistical analysis of the results showed that teachers assessed this skill of the students in the Intervention group as statistically higher than the same skill of the Control group. Creative reading and writing, however, may have enhanced the students' ability to support and praise others in their efforts or even use humour in creating a positive classroom climate, but it should be emphasized that it is not intended to improve these skills in the short term. Rather, it may assist in long-term improvements in terms of encouragement.

For this reason, it needs to be further investigated whether and to what extent students who appear to have acquired or enhanced this skill will retain it over time, compared to those students who did not implement the 13 creative reading and writing workshops. It should also be emphasized that any programme aimed at enhancing students' intrapersonal or interpersonal skills has a positive impact when implemented from early childhood and continues throughout an individual's academic career. They are certainly not a panacea, but they are tools of great importance for the academic, social and emotional learning of all children.

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